

TABLE 1—COLOUR, ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA OF OXOVANADIUM(IV) COMPLEXES OF THE SCHIFF BASES

Compounds ^a	Colour	Decomp. point (°C)	Analysis %			μ_{eff} (B.M.)
			V	N	H ₂ O	
VOSg H ₂ O	Blue	210	19.3 (19.47) ^b	5.2 (5.35)	6.6 (6.87)	1.79
VOSa H ₂ O	Greyish green	225	16.5 (16.38)	4.2 (4.49)	5.5 (5.77)	1.96
VOSal H ₂ O	Light green	245	18.0 (18.48)	4.9 (5.07)	6.5 (6.53)	1.86
VOHg H ₂ O	Blue	220	18.4 (18.48)	4.7 (5.07)	6.2 (6.53)	1.45
VOHa H ₂ O	Deep blue	235	14.8 (15.08)	4.1 (4.14)	5.2 (5.32)	1.45
VOHal H ₂ O	Light blue	255	17.4 (17.69)	4.7 (4.83)	6.0 (6.21)	1.49
VOAg H ₂ O	Bluish green	270	21.3 (21.26)	5.6 (5.83)	7.5 (7.50)	1.77
VOAa H ₂ O	Brown	280	16.6 (16.89)	4.5 (4.63)	5.8 (5.96)	1.88
VOAal H ₂ O	Blue	250	19.8 (20.18)	5.3 (5.51)	7.0 (7.09)	1.83

a. S, H and A stand for salicylidene, *o*-hydroxyacetophenone and acetylacetonate moiety, respectively and g, a and al stand for glycine, anthranilic acid and β -alanine moiety, respectively of the corresponding Schiff bases.

b. Values in the parentheses are theoretical values.

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Complexes of Copper(II), Nickel(II), Cobalt(II) and Iron(II) with Schiff's Bases Derived from 2-Pyrrolidone and Aromatic Amines

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CONDENSATION of 2-pyrrolidone with aromatic amines produces Schiff's bases with the following structure :

X = H ; *o*-, *m*- or *p*-CH₃

These are expected to act as bidentate ligands with the possibilities of donation from the NH and azomethine groups. Although a large number of Schiff's base complexes are reported, these ligands have not been studied till now. The present paper records the synthesis and characterisation of some complexes of these with copper(II), nickel(II), cobalt(II) and iron(II).

The Schiff's bases were obtained *in situ* by refluxing 2-pyrrolidone (1.0 mole) with an aromatic amine (1.0 mole), such as aniline, *o*-, *m*- or *p*-toluidine, in methanol for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled, a calculated amount of solid metal(II) sulphate in finely powdered form was added and was refluxed again. The reaction was stopped after 10 hr and the solid complexes which are blue, yellow, violet, pink or brown in colour were filtered and dried. These could not be recrystallised due to their insolubility in common solvents but were washed repeatedly with methanol for purification.

On the basis of elemental analysis the formulae of the complexes are $\text{MSO}_4 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2 \cdot \text{A}$, where M = Cu(II) or Ni(II) and $\text{MSO}_4 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_4 \cdot \text{A}$, where M = Co(II) or Fe(II). The complexes, though insoluble in water, methanol and dimethylformamide, are soluble enough in nitrobenzene with the molar conductance values ($10^{-3} M$) in the range 20-26 mhos, suggesting that the anion is not coordinated. The molecular formulae of the complexes are thus truly represented as $[\text{M}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{A}]\text{SO}_4$ and $[\text{M}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4\text{A}]\text{SO}_4$ and hence only one molecule of ligand along with two or four molecules of water are coordinated to metal(II) ions. The Cu(II) or Ni(II) complexes are thus tetra and Co(II) or Fe(II) complexes are hexa-coordinated in nature.

The evidence for coordination of ligands is obtained by ir spectra. All the complexes exhibit

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA

Sl. No.	Complex	Colour	Analysis %					Δ in mhos in nitrobenzene	μ_{eff} B.M.
			M	C	H	N	SO ₄		
1.	[Cu(H ₂ O) ₂ (C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃)]SO ₄	Bottle green	17.02 (17.88)*	34.20 (33.70)	4.90 (4.51)	6.98 (7.88)	26.50 (27.00)	24.98	1.94
2.	[Cu(H ₂ O) ₂ (o-C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₃)]SO ₄	Bottle green	16.80 (17.01)	35.20 (35.93)	3.98 (4.90)	7.98 (7.62)	26.50 (26.11)	25.84	1.83
3.	[Cu(H ₂ O) ₂ (m-C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₃)]SO ₄	Blue	16.50 (17.01)	35.50 (35.92)	3.99 (4.90)	8.02 (7.62)	26.50 (26.11)	23.50	2.14
4.	[Cu(H ₂ O) ₂ (p-C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₃)]SO ₄	Dark blue	17.51 (17.01)	36.50 (35.93)	5.02 (4.90)	8.50 (7.62)	26.30 (26.11)	27.52	2.04
5.	[Ni(H ₂ O) ₂ (C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃)]SO ₄	Yellowish green	16.50 (16.81)	33.95 (34.20)	4.28 (4.58)	7.60 (7.98)	26.90 (27.34)	20.68	1.21
6.	[Ni(H ₂ O) ₂ (o-C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₃)]SO ₄	Yellowish green	16.70 (16.17)	36.58 (36.18)	4.50 (4.92)	7.92 (7.67)	26.90 (26.30)	26.50	1.28
7.	[Ni(H ₂ O) ₂ (m-C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₃)]SO ₄	Yellow	15.80 (16.17)	35.90 (36.18)	4.02 (4.92)	7.30 (7.67)	25.98 (26.30)	24.52	0.87
8.	[Ni(H ₂ O) ₂ (p-C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₃)]SO ₄	Yellow	16.28 (16.17)	36.50 (36.18)	5.08 (4.92)	8.02 (7.67)	26.90 (26.30)	20.85	1.08
9.	[Co(H ₂ O) ₂ (C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃)]SO ₄	Purple	14.90 (15.23)	30.90 (31.01)	5.50 (5.17)	7.60 (7.24)	24.30 (24.81)	21.60	5.08
10.	[Co(H ₂ O) ₂ (o-C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₃)]SO ₄	Dark pink	14.02 (14.65)	32.52 (32.85)	5.00 (5.47)	6.35 (6.97)	23.75 (23.90)	26.82	5.09
11.	[Co(H ₂ O) ₂ (m-C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₃)]SO ₄	Purple	15.08 (14.65)	33.12 (32.85)	5.90 (5.47)	7.05 (6.97)	24.50 (23.90)	21.54	5.21
12.	[Co(H ₂ O) ₂ (p-C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₃)]SO ₄	Purple	15.50 (14.68)	32.20 (32.85)	5.02 (5.47)	6.50 (6.97)	23.20 (23.90)	22.68	5.12
13.	[Fe(H ₂ O) ₂ (C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃)]SO ₄	Brownish pink	13.90 (14.56)	31.59 (31.29)	5.70 (5.21)	7.60 (7.31)	24.80 (25.02)	24.60	5.02
14.	[Fe(H ₂ O) ₂ (o-C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₃)]SO ₄	Light brown	13.85 (14.02)	32.95 (33.10)	5.55 (5.52)	6.90 (7.02)	24.52 (24.07)	22.60	5.10
15.	[Fe(H ₂ O) ₂ (m-C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₃)]SO ₄	Brown	14.30 (14.02)	33.55 (33.10)	5.70 (5.52)	7.80 (7.02)	24.50 (24.07)	20.95	5.01
16.	[Fe(H ₂ O) ₂ (p-C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₃)]SO ₄	Brown	14.51 (14.02)	33.40 (33.10)	5.90 (5.52)	7.10 (7.02)	24.58 (24.07)	21.40	5.08

* Figures in the parentheses are calculated values.

a sharp but broad band around 3400 cm⁻¹, due to the OH stretching frequency. The negative shift of this band as well as the appearance of rocking and wagging modes at 900 and 700 cm⁻¹ in complexes suggest that the water molecules are coordinated¹⁻⁴. The coordination of ligand A through NH and azomethine groups is indicated by the lowering of NH stretching frequency of free ligand by 100 cm⁻¹ or so, and the presence of azomethine stretch in complexes at 1600 ± 10 cm⁻¹ (the same in free ligand occurs at 1630 cm⁻¹)⁵⁻⁸. It is thus clear that the Schiff's base acts as a bidentate ligand.

The geometries of the complexes have been established by magnetic and electronic spectral data as discussed below.

Copper(II) complexes: The μ_{eff} values of the complexes are around 1.90 B.M. characteristic of one unpaired electron. In electronic spectra, one main band and one or two shoulders are seen in the visible region around 13.50, 14.60 and 10.64 kK, respectively and are assigned as ²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g}, ²B_{1g} → ²B_{2g} and ²B_{1g} → ²A_{2g}, corresponding to the tetracoordinated planar structures. The Dq values, which are around 1300 cm⁻¹, support this geometry.

Nickel(II) complexes: The complexes are diamagnetic with the μ_{eff} values lying in the range 0.80 B.M. These values as well as the yellow colour of the complexes suggest a planar structure. The same

indication is confirmed by the electronic spectra where two well defined transitions ν_2 and ν_3 are observed between 13.50-17.50 kK and 22.00-25.00 kK being due to ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g} transitions, respectively. Another weak band (ν_1) occurs between 12.00-13.00 kK^{9,10}. The maximum of the ν_2 band is equal to Dq and the same thus lies around 1560 cm⁻¹.

Cobalt(II) complexes: These complexes possess high spin octahedral structures as shown by their μ_{eff} values of 5.00 B.M. and the presence of two sharp bands at 20.00 and 9.90 kK. These correspond to ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P) and ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(F) transitions. The ν_2 or the ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{2g}(F) transition is seen in the form of a very weak band at 18.00 kK. The Dq and B values are around 850 and 980 cm⁻¹.

Iron(II) complexes: The complexes are high spin and μ_{eff} lies around 5.10 B.M. In the diffuse reflectance spectra, the band corresponding to the octahedral ⁶T_{2g} → ⁶E_g transition appears at 10.70 kK. The dark pink or brown colours of the complexes are due to the presence of a band at 24.00 kK accompanied by a shoulder at 16.80 kK. The Dq value is around 1070 cm⁻¹ and confirms the pseudo-octahedral structures of the complexes.

These compounds belong to a class of mixed ligand complexes as two different ligands are coordi-

nated to metal(II) ion, and the Dq values indicate that the ligand field around the metal is sufficiently strong. The values of Racah parameters calculated for some complexes further suggest a considerable degree of covalency or orbital overlap in the complexes^{11,12}.

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Complexes of Sulphamethizole with Copper and Silver

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TRANSITIONAL metals like Fe, Co, Ag, Au, Cu have long been used in medicines. Kaushal and coworkers^{1,2} have prepared a large number of metal sulphonamide complexes, some of which are found to be more potent than the parent sulphonamides. Keeping this in view, complexes of sulphamethizole (I) with cupric chloride and silver nitrate were prepared by us.

Experimental

Composition of the complex: Standard solutions of cupric chloride (0.02 M), silver nitrate (0.02 M) and sulphamethizole (0.01 M) were prepared in spectroscopically pure ethanol. 10 ml of the ligand was diluted to 50 ml and titrated against the metal salt solutions using 'Tosniwal' conductivity

bridge and dip type electrodes at 28°. The results after volume corrections indicate 2 : 1 sulphamethizole cupric chloride complex and 1 : 1 sulphamethizole silver nitrate complex, respectively (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

The nature of the copper complex was also studied spectrophotometrically using Vasburgh and Cooper³ method. For this, mixtures containing 2 : 1, 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 proportions of equimolecular solutions of sulphamethizole and cupric chloride (0.04 M) in spectroscopically pure ethanol were taken and the absorbances measured. The results indicated that only one complex with 2 : 1 ratio is formed. Formation of 2 : 1 complex was further confirmed by Job's method of continuous variation⁴ using absorbance as the index property (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2.

Isolation and analysis:

Sulphamethizole-cupric chloride complex: Sulphamethizole (2.5 g) and cupric chloride (0.8 g) in 2 : 1 molar proportions were dissolved separately in minimum quantity of absolute alcohol. The base solution was added slowly to the metal salt solution with constant stirring. A dark green solution was